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- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
- 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
- 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
- 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
- 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
- 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
- 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
- 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
- 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
- 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
- 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
- 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
- 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
- 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
- 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

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Pedagogika, psixologiya fanlariga ixtisoslashgan ilmiy jurnal

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MUNDARIJA

Maktabga tayyorlov guruhi tarbiyalanuvchilarini maktab ta'limiga tayyorligini aniqlash	16
<i>Akramova Dildora Ergashboy qizi</i>	
Bola tarbiyasida o'yinning ahamiyati	21
<i>Choriyeva Durdona Anvarovna, O'ktamova Nasiba Ravshan qizi</i>	
O'quvchilarning loyiha-tadqiqot faoliyatini tashkil etishning ilmiy asoslari	25
<i>Sobirova Nilufar Azimboy qizi</i>	
Maktabgacha ta'lim tashkilotlarida pedagogik jarayonni tashkil etish	29
<i>Choriyeva Durdona Anvarovna, Ko'zibayeva Nasiba O'tkir qizi</i>	
Maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarda sensor tarbiyani rivojlantirish texnologiyalari	32
<i>Choriyeva Durdona Anvarovna, Allaberdiyeva Mardona O'tkirbek qizi</i>	
Maktabgacha ta'lim yoshidagi bolalarni jismoniy tarbiyalash mazmuni va vazifalari.....	37
<i>Choriyeva Durdona Anvarovna, Mirsharfova Shahinabegim Saidabbos qizi</i>	
Gandbolchi sportchilarni jismoniy tayyorgarligida harakatli o'yinlarning tarbiyaviy rivojlantiruvchi vazifalari	41
<i>Ibodullayeva Munira Atabek qizi</i>	
Boshlang'ich sinflarda dars samaradorligini oshirishda noan'anaviy usullardan foydalanish samaradorligi.....	44
<i>Yusufaliyeva Gulnora Abduraxmonovna</i>	
Modern Requirements for a Teacher's Pedagogical Skills in the Context of Digital Transformation in Education.....	49
<i>Abira Bakhramova</i>	
Ta'lim muassasalarida o'smir yoshlarning ijtimoiylashuv jarayonini samarali tashkil etishga yordam beruvchi pedagogik omillar va shart-sharoitlar	54
<i>Artikova Gulnoza Xasanovna</i>	
Maktabgacha ta'lim tashkilotlarida iqtisodiy tarbiya berishning nazariy-pedagogik asoslari	57
<i>Mamadaliyeva Nilufar Bahodirovna</i>	
Kognitiv lingvistika va konseptologiya masalalari.....	60
<i>Meyliqulova Manzura Abdullayevna</i>	
Developing Law Students' Writing Competence Through the IRAC Method in Legal English Classes: A Comprehensive Study at TSUL.....	63
<i>Noila Mustafojeva</i>	
Tarixiy obidalarning restavratsiya jarayonlarining o'rganilish tarixi	67
<i>Ochilov Davron Bahodir o'g'li</i>	
Oliy ta'limda baholash jarayonini avtomatlashtirishda sun'iy intellekt texnologiyalarining qo'llanishi.....	72
<i>Ovxunov Iqboljon Abdunabiyevich, Mamadaliyeva Kamolaxon Xayrullo qizi</i>	
Tabiiy yorug'lik va barqaror energiya manbalarini integratsiyalashgan mini home loyihasi.....	76
<i>Djuraboyev Maqsudbek Karimbek o'g'li, Qodirjonov Oyatillo Abdulboqi o'g'li</i>	
Talabalarning tarixiy tafakkurini rivojlantirishda madaniy meros vositalarining pedagogik ahamiyati.....	80
<i>Rajabova Matluba Toshkentboy qizi</i>	
Maktabgacha ta'lim tashkiloti tarbiyachilarining umummadaniy kompetensiyalarini rivojlantirish texnologiyalari.....	83
<i>Saidova Nigora Olimovna, Jo'rayeva Nilufar Rustamjon qizi</i>	
Raqamli kommunikatsiyalarni o'smirlar shaxsiyatining rivojlanishiga ta'siri	86
<i>Shomurotova Nigoraxon Nabijonovna</i>	
Talabalarning chizma geometriya fanini mustaqil bilish faoliyatiga oid kompetensiyalarini "Visio" dasturi vositasida rivojlantirish metodikasi	90
<i>Tashimov Nurlan Erpolatovich</i>	

Shaxslararo munosabatlar – ijtimoiy pedagogik muammo sifatida.....	94
<i>Uralova Muxabbat Sanjar qizi</i>	
O'zbek tili darslarida raqamli ta'lim vositalaridan foydalanish tajribasi	98
<i>Yuldasheva Dilnoza Bekmurodovna</i>	
Психологическая готовность разведенных людей к вступлению в новый брак и приоритеты при выборе партнера.....	101
<i>Саидвалиева Шодия Рихсихужа кизи</i>	
Воспитание любви к прекрасному у дошкольников в развивающей предметно-пространственной среде: теоретико-методический аспект.....	107
<i>Терехова Ольга Евгеньевна, Темирова Барно Кёмхоновна</i>	
Методика формирования наблюдательности у детей 6–7 лет в процессе целенаправленных прогулок-наблюдений.....	111
<i>Терехова Ольга Евгеньевна, Шокиржонова Мохира Илхомжон кизи</i>	
Bo'lajak tarbiyachilarni kasbiy pedagogik faoliyatga tayyorlash texnologiyalari	115
<i>Artikbayeva Aziza Abror qizi</i>	
Zamonaviy darslarda guruhlarda ishlash metodikasi	118
<i>Berdiyeva Lobar Norqobulovna</i>	
Maktabgacha ta'lim tashkilotlarida faol rivojlantiruvchi muhitni tashkil etishda STEAM ta'lim texnologiyasidan foydalanish.....	120
<i>Esanova Maysara Umirovna</i>	
Logopediyada axborot texnologiyalarini qo'llash metodlari	124
<i>Feruz Yusupova Akildjanovna</i>	
Axborot texnologiyalarining ta'lim jarayonidagi o'rni va rivojlanish bosqichlari.....	130
<i>Qodirov Farrux Ergash o'g'li, Allanazarova Anora Muxobir qizi</i>	
Bo'lajak boshlang'ich sinf o'qituvchilarining ilmiy-ijodiy kompetentsiyalarini rivojlantirish	134
<i>Umarov Xusniddin</i>	
Bo'lajak talabalarning individual yondashuv asosida kasbiy-ijodiy ko'nikmalarini rivojlantirish	138
<i>Arslonova Gulsora Kurbonovna</i>	
Ona tili darslarida til kompetensiyasini kognitiv-semantik yondashuv asosida shakllantirish	142
<i>Mo'minova Go'zalxon G'ulamjanovna</i>	
Bo'lajak boshlang'ich sinf o'qituvchilarining ijodiy tafakkurini rivojlantirishning pedagogik shart-sharoitlari	147
<i>Maxliyo Turoпова Erkin qizi</i>	
Talabalarning kreativligini musiqiy-nazariy fanlar vositasida oshirish samaradorligi	153
<i>Urinova Sabina Shuxrat qizi</i>	
Imijning ijtimoiy-psixologik fenomen sifatida talqini	160
<i>Jo'rayeva Sohibjamol Norqobilovna</i>	
Inklyuziv kompetensiya tushunchasining ilmiy-nazariy asoslari	163
<i>Abdubannobova Mahliyo Abdurashid qizi</i>	
Boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarining ijtimoiy-emotsional kompetensiyalarini rivojlantirish texnologiyalari	167
<i>Abdurasulova Dilnoza Abdug'ani qizi</i>	
Muxammas (taxmis) janrining o'zbek she'riyatidagi tarixiy taraqqiyoti va zamonaviy poetik talqinlari	170
<i>Avazova Sitara</i>	
Maktabgacha ta'lim tashkiloti va ota-onalar hamkorining asosiy shakllari.....	173
<i>Babayeva Dono Razzakovna, Erkinova Madinabonu Otabek qizi, Xolmatova O'g'lioy Tojiddin qizi</i>	
Yangi taraqqiyot davrida talaba-yoshlarni oilaviy hayotga tayyorlashning ijtimoiy-pedagogik muammo sifatida	177
<i>Botirova Zohida Doniyor qizi</i>	
Logoritmikada sportga asoslangan o'yinlar	180
<i>Dilfuza Ochilova Zayniddinovna</i>	
Jismoniy tarbiyaning o'quvchilarning kognitiv rivojlanishiga ta'siri (Andijon shahridagi Prezident maktabi tajribasi asosida).....	184
<i>Ibragimov Shuhratbek Iminjonovich</i>	

MUNDARIJA СОДЕРЖАНИЕ CONTENTS

Bolajak tarbiyachilarni tarbiyaviy faoliyatga tayyorlashda integrativ yondashuvning zaruriyati	188
Karimova Feruzaxon Zakirovna	
Effective Techniques of Teaching Foreign Language Classes: a Sample of The 4CS Method	191
Khaitmuratova Zarina Sobirdjanovna	
Maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarni intellektual imkoniyatlarini tabiat bilan tanishtirish orqali shakllantirish ..	193
Maxmudova Durdona Mirkarimovna	
O'quvchilarning kasbiy ma'naviy dunyoqarashini shakllantirishning pedagogik xususiyatlari	196
Mutallibjonov Ma'rufjon	
Maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarni kun tartibini to'g'ri tashkil etish	200
Muxtorova Mohira Ma'rufjon qizi	
Aksiologik yondashuv asosida altruistik ko'nikmalarni shakllantirish jarayonida ijtimoiy faoliyatni amalga oshirish	204
Norboyeva Moxigul Shavkat qizi	
O'smirlarda agressiv xulq-atvorini psixologik o'rganishning o'ziga xos xususiyatlari	207
Norqulova Dildora Shavkat qizi	
Raqamlashtirish jarayonida bo'lajak muhandislarni ishlab chiqarish-texnologik faoliyatiga tayyorlashning dasturiy-metodik ta'minoti	211
Nurov O'tkir Xudoyberdiyevich	
Zamonaviy pedagogik texnologiyalarni amaliyotga joriy etilish	214
O'roqova Zilola Salomovna	
Pedagogika ta'lim yo'nalishi talabalarida amaliy tayyorgarlik tushunchasi va uning mazmun-mohiyati	217
Qaramanov Obid Xudayberdiyevich	
Pedagoglar uchun sun'iy intellekt asosidagi shaxsiylashtirilgan ta'lim imkoniyatlari	221
Qarshiyev Jamshid Murotaliyevich	
Talabalarda psixologik moslashuvchanlikda refleksiya mohiyati va kognitiv qobiliyatni rivojlantirish samaradorligi	226
Ravshanova Nargiza Norboyevna	
Maktabgacha ta'lim tashkilotlarida integrallashgan mashg'ulotarni tashkil etish	230
S. Irisova	
Maktabgacha ta'lim tashkilotlarida marketing faoliyatini tizimli tashkil etishning nazariy asoslari	233
Sadikova Dilafuz Xusanovna, Qo'chqorova Munisa Anvar qizi	
Maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarning dialogik nutqini xalq ertaklari asosida rivojlantirish	237
Seitmuratova Venera Jumamuratovna, Abdurafova Muxayyo Xabibullo qizi	
Bolalarni maktabga tayyorlashda psixologik yondashuv	241
Seitmuratova Venera Jumamuratovna, Sanoqulova Gulasal Nurillo qizi	
Sun'iy intellektni tibbiy oliy ta'lim o'quv dasturlarini ishlab chiqishda qo'llash: innovatsion yondashuvlar va tajribalar	246
Toxirova Farida Olimjonovna	
Talabalarni estetik tarbiyalashda milliy xalq o'yinlaridan foydalanish modeli	251
Usarov Murodjon Mamarasul o'g'li	
Xalqaro kimyo olimpiadalariga o'quvchilarni tayyorlashda xalqaro baholash tadqiqotlariga asoslangan kreativ topshiriqlar va fanlararo integratsiyadan foydalanish metodikasi	254
Usmanov Baxtiyor Xabibullayevich	
Xoja (Sayyid Poshshoxoja ibn Abdulvahhobxo'ja) va uning asarlarining o'zbek nasridagi o'рни va ahamiyati	258
Valijonova Mahzunabonu	
Maktabgacha ta'lim tashkilotlari boshqaruvida diversifikatsiya: tizimli yondashuv va rivojlanish strategiyalari	261
Xakimova Sevara Shavkat qizi	
STEAM texnologiyasini nodavlat ta'lim tashkilotlarida ommalashtirishning ijobiy tomonlari	264
Xalokova Maksudaxon Ergashevna, Melnikova Zaynura	
Muhammad Sodiq Qoshg'ariy asarlarida ma'naviy-axloqiy tarbiya nazariyasi	267
Moxira Niyozqulova Nuraliyevna	

Sun'iy intellekt texnologiyalari asosida bo'lajak boshlang'ich sinf o'qituvchilarining ona tili fanini o'qitish kompetentligini rivojlantirish metodikasi (AQSh tajribasi).....	270
<i>Olimjonova Dilnavoz Maribjon qizi</i>	
Xalqaro baholash dasturlari mohiyati va ahamiyati	274
<i>Vohidova Ibodot Hurmatullayevna</i>	
Maktabgacha ta'lim tashkilotlari ta'lim-tarbiya jarayonida shaxsga yo'naltirilgan yondashuv.....	277
<i>Xujamiyarov Sa'dullo Choriyevich</i>	
Davlat-xususiy sheriklik asosidagi nodavlat maktabgacha ta'lim tashkilotlarida jamoatchilik nazorati samaradorligini oshirish mexanizmlarini takomillashtirish.....	281
<i>Xusanova Dilraxon Botiraliyevna</i>	
Talabalarning jismoniy tayyorgarligida suzish mashg'ulotlarining ta'siri	285
<i>Zuxriddin Nasibovich Boboshev</i>	
Bo'lajak o'qituvchilarni milliy-ma'naviy qadryatlar asosida tayyorlashning o'ziga xos xususiyatlari	289
<i>Abdullayev Muxammadimin Egamberdiyevich, Dadabayev Akramjon Askaraliyevich</i>	
Использование чат-ботов в образовательном процессе.....	294
<i>Мадаминова Наргизахон Жахонгир кизи</i>	
Формирование гендерной культуры детей старшего дошкольного возраста в контексте государственной стратегии Узбекистана	298
<i>Намазбаева Лола Закировна, Тиллабаева Малика Хабибуллаевна</i>	
STEAM технологии в дошкольном образовании.....	302
<i>Садикова Дилафруз Хусановна</i>	
Системная модель социально-эмоционального обучения в Узбекистане: интеграция подходов, основанных на школьном образовании и партнерстве семьи и школы	307
<i>Санакулова Нигора</i>	
Oila qurish yoshidagi talabalar psixologik xususiyatlari.....	311
<i>Qo'ziyeva Gulzoda Shermat qizi</i>	
Ingliz tili nutq faoliyati turlarini rivojlantirishda leksik-assotsiativ tarmoqlardan foydalanishning lingvodidaktik asoslari.....	315
<i>Mirzakamolova Maftuna Rahimjon qizi</i>	
Talabalarga ingliz tilidagi matnlarni kommunikativ metod yordamida o'qish texnikasini takomillashtirish usullari.....	318
<i>Mo'minova Mahliyo Axrorjonovna</i>	
Bo'lajak boshlang'ich sinf o'qituvchilarini o'quvchilarning mantiqiy fikrlashini rivojlantirishda ona tili mashqlarining roli	321
<i>Boltayeva Guzal Tolibovna</i>	
Bo'lajak tarbiyachilarning kreativ kompetensiyalarini rivojlantirish	324
<i>Ziyayeva Umida Turaxodjayevna</i>	
Maktabgacha hamda boshlang'ich maktab yoshidagi bolalar jismoniy tarbiyasi tizimini modernizatsiya qilishning innovatsion istiqbollari	327
<i>A'zamov Ruhullo Mahmudjon o'g'li</i>	
Boshlang'ich sinflarda informatika fanini o'qitishning maqsadlari va vazifalari.....	333
<i>Alikulova Bibisora Abdulvokhobovna</i>	
Bola shaxsini rivojlantirishda axborot-kommunikatsion texnologiyalarning pedagogik ahamiyati	336
<i>Azimova Dilnoza Sherzodovna</i>	
Raqamli didaktika sharoitida oliy ta'limni raqamlashtirishning nazariy asoslari va pedagogik xususiyatlari	339
<i>Berdikulova Shaxnoza Erkinjon qizi</i>	
Boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarining aqliy qobiliyatini shakllantirishda dars va darsdan tashqari mashg'ulotlarda shaxmat o'yinidan foydalanish imkoniyatlar	343
<i>Boboqulov Chori Urolovich</i>	

O'zbek tilidagi "kasb-hunar" va "lavozim-amal" konseptlarining hozirgi zamon o'zbek tili konseptosferasidagi o'rni.....	348
Dexqonova Muattarxon Ilxomovna	
O'quv jarayonida ijtimoiy tarmoqlar orqali bilim almashishning didaktik imkoniyatlari va metodologik asoslari.....	352
Ernazarov Alisher Ergashevich, Pimkulova Stora Boltayevna	
"Intellekt xarita" yordamida o'quvchilarga qattiq jismlarning solishtirma issiqlik sig'imini mavzusini tushuntirish va ularning to'la fikrlash ko'nikmalarini rivojlantirish.....	358
Eshboboyeva Muxlisa Zavqiy qizi	
Inklyuziv ta'lim texnologiyalari	363
Fayzullayeva Shoira Shorahmatovna	
Oliy pedagogik ta'lim tizimida hamkorlikda ta'lim nazariyasi va amaliyoti	366
Hojiyeva Zulfiya O'ktamovna	
Hikoya tuzishga o'rgatish maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarning bog'lanishli nutqini rivojlantirishning muhim vositasi sifatida.....	369
Imixanova Nodira Saidburxon qizi	
Professional Competency Development of Future English Language Teachers: A Framework for the 21 st Century	374
Kamoldin Tadjiboyev	
Bo'lajak tarbiya fani o'qituvchilarining kasbiy tayyorgarligi jarayonida raqamli texnologiyalardan foydalanishning nazariy asoslari.....	378
Nosirova Dilfuza	
Inklyuziv sinf muhitida zaif eshituvchi bolalar bilan musiqa mashg'ulotlarini tashkil etishning nazariy yondashuvlari.....	383
Qizlarxon Isomova	
Raqamli ta'lim muhitida mustaqil ta'limni rivojlantirishda zamonaviy texnologiyalar	389
Shabdullayeva Lazokatxon Orifbekovna	
Boshlang'ich sinflarda perimetr, yuza va hajmni o'rganish metodikasi samaradorligini shakllantirish	392
Shodmonova Madina Otabek qizi	
Chiziqli operatorlarning spektral xossalari	398
Sultonboyeva Zuhra Bobomurod qizi	
Qisqa masofaga yuguruvchilar ish qobiliyatini oshirish usullari.....	402
Utayev Z. M.	
Neyropedagogik yondashuv asosida 9–11 yoshli o'quvchilarda ingliz tilida matnни o'qib tushunish ko'nikmalarini rivojlantirishda ijro funksiyalarining o'rni	408
Xolboyeva Nodiraxon Abdumalik qizi	
Bo'lajak o'qituvchilarni kasbiy faoliyatga tayyorlash muammosining dolzarbligi.....	413
Yo'ldosheva Dilnura Nizomjon qizi	
Bo'lg'usi tarbiyachilarda grafik organayzerlar vositasida ekologik tarbiyani shakllantirish usullari	416
O. Xo'janiyozova, Yuldashova Sanamjon Bobomurod qizi	
Взаимодействие воспитателей и родителей в процессе формирования нравственных представлений дошкольников.....	419
Жураева Наргиза Таировна, Абдуллаева Халимахон Дилёрна	
Развитие государственно-частного партнёрства в сфере дошкольного образования Республики Узбекистан	423
Курбанова Нуржамал Бахбергеновна	
Talaba qizlarning jismoniy va funksional tayyorgarligini shakllantirishning ilmiy metodologik asoslari.....	426
M. M. Ma'rufov, Sh. R. Ma'rufova	
Развитие языковых навыков у дошкольников через игровые методы обучения английскому языку	430
Садикова Шоиста Акбаровна	
"Узбекский текст в русской литературе XX–XXI веков..."	433
Сулаймонова Дурдонахон Равшан кизи, Иванова Ирина Николаевна	

Механизмы использования цифровых педагогических технологий для обеспечения непрерывности образовательного процесса учащих начальных классов в условиях длительного лечения.....	437
Турсунова Д. З., Холлиева Н. Х.	
Патриотическое воспитание будущих педагогов: совершенствование методики формирования любви к родине в условиях профессиональной подготовки.....	440
Шарипова Холида Дехкановна	
Sun'iy intellekt texnologiyalarining oliy ta'limdagi ahamiyati: universitet talabalari va ta'lim sifatiga ta'siri, global o'zgarishlar.....	444
Mambetniyozov Maksetbay Torebekovich	
Interpretable Artificial Intelligence in Pedagogical Diagnostics and Math Performance Prediction: A Systematic Review of Applications in International Standardized Assessments.....	449
Diana Dushabaeva	
Ona tili ta'limida intellektual ta'lim tizimlaridan foydalanishning metodik tamoyillari (boshlang'ich ta'lim yo'nalishi misolida).....	454
Djakbarova Mahliyo Ibraximjonovna	
Boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarining ingliz tilidagi kommunikativ kompetensiyani multimedia vositalari asosida shakllantirishning metodik shart-sharoitlari.....	457
Moxinur G'ulomova Inomjon qizi	
Talaba qizlarda ijtimoiy faolligini rivojlantirishning pedagogik asoslari.....	462
Nurmatova Nargiza Ulug'bekovna	
Raqamli ta'lim muhitida mustaqil ta'lim kompetensiyasini shakllantirishning nazariy asoslari	466
Utayeva Iroda Baxodirovna, Ochilova Namuna Mirzohid qizi	
Interaction Between Teacher and Students in the Process of Mastering University Subjects.....	469
Sadriyev Nizom Najmiddinovich, Usarov Nuriddin	
Концептуальные подходы к исследованию конкурентоспособности университетов	472
Менглиева Индира Баходировна	
Talabalarning ilmiy-tadqiqot faoliyatini tashkil etishning guruhlar va diskussiyaga asoslangan shakllari (xalqaro tajriba misolida)	475
Xamroyeva Feruza Asrorovna, Ibragimov A'lamjon Amrulloevich	
Ratsional turmush tarzi: nazariy poydevor, psixologik mexanizmlar va amaliy strategiyalar.....	478
Bekmuradov Zarif Xurramovich	
Boshlang'ich sinflarda folklor janrlarini o'qitishda innovatsion pedtexnologiyalardan foydalanish	483
Adizova Nodira Baxtiyorovna	
Dialogik nutqda to'liqsiz gaplarning funksional–sintaktik xususiyatlari (ingliz va o'zbek tillari misolida).....	488
Artikova Nodirabegim Sanakulovna	
Maktabga tayyorlov guruhi tarbiyalanuvchilarini tevarak-atrof bilan tanishtirishda ekologik qadriyatlarining roli.....	492
Ernyazova Manzura Amankeldi qizi	
Boshlang'ich sinf darslarini samarali tashkil etishda pedagogik mahoratning ahamiyati	496
Kamolitdinova Kamolotxon Muxammadjalilovna	
Masofaviy ta'lim jarayonida seven skillsni rivojlantirishning pedagogik va psixologik asoslari.....	499
Nurmetova Nazokat Baxtiyorovna, Masharipova Durdona Raximbergen qizi	
Teacher Competency and Professional Development in Non-Native English Countries: The Karakalpakstan Perspective.....	506
Mamirbaeva Dina, Pirnazarova Mekhiyban	
Maktabgacha ta'limda rivojlanish markazlari integratsiyasi asosida tayanch kompetensiyalarni shakllantirishning pedagogik asoslari.....	510
Raxmatova Maftuna Uktamjan qizi	
Milliy kurash texnikasi va taktikasi.....	513
Xomudjonova Feruza, Panjiyeva Gulzoda	
Boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarida kognitiv qobiliyatlarni rivojlantirish bosqichlari	517
Xurramova Lobarxon Akramjonovna	
Развитие сотрудничества у детей старшего дошкольного возраста в проектной деятельности	521
Аллаева Наргиза Уктамовна	

TEACHER COMPETENCY AND PROFESSIONAL DEVELOPMENT IN NON-NATIVE ENGLISH COUNTRIES: THE KARAKALPAKSTAN PERSPECTIVE

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Abstract: This article examines teacher competency and professional development in non-native English contexts, focusing on Karakalpakstan, Uzbekistan. Using mixed methods, the study analyzes national reforms, certification policies, and CPD programs influencing English teachers' pedagogical and linguistic development. The findings reveal high engagement in professional development but uneven impact due to contextual, institutional, and psychological barriers. The study emphasizes contextualized CPD, intercultural competence, and sustained mentoring as key factors for sustainable teacher professionalism.

Key words: teacher competency, professional development, EFL teachers, Karakalpakstan, CPD, educational reform.

Annotatsiya: Maqolada ingliz tili ona tili bo'lmagan mamlakatlar sharoitida o'qituvchilarning kasbiy kompetensiyasi va uzluksiz kasbiy rivojlanishi Qoraqalpog'iston misolida tahlil qilinadi. Tadqiqotda milliy islohotlar, sertifikatlash siyosati va malaka oshirish dasturlarining ingliz tili o'qituvchilarining pedagogik hamda til kompetensiyalariga ta'siri o'rganiladi. Natijalar o'qituvchilarning yuqori faolligini ko'rsatadi, biroq kontekstual, institutsional va psixologik to'siqlar sababli ta'sir darajasi bir xil emas. Maqolada kontekstga moslashtirilgan uzluksiz kasbiy rivojlanish, madaniyatlararo kompetensiya va barqaror mentorlikning ahamiyati ta'kidlanadi.

Kalit so'zlar: o'qituvchi kompetensiyasi, kasbiy rivojlanish, ingliz tili o'qituvchilari, Qoraqalpog'iston, uzluksiz kasbiy rivojlanish, ta'lim islohotlari.

Аннотация: В статье рассматриваются профессиональные компетенции и повышение квалификации учителей английского языка в неанглоязычной среде на примере Каракалпакстана. На основе смешанных методов анализа изучается влияние национальных реформ, сертификационных требований и программ непрерывного профессионального развития на педагогический и языковой рост учителей. Результаты показывают высокий уровень вовлеченности учителей при наличии контекстуальных, институциональных и психологических барьеров. Подчеркивается необходимость контекстуализированного повышения квалификации, межкультурной компетентности и устойчивых наставнических моделей.

Ключевые слова: профессиональная компетентность, повышение квалификации, учителя английского языка, Каракалпакстан, непрерывное профессиональное развитие, образовательные реформы.

INTRODUCTION

In the current globalized era, the proficiency and pedagogical competence of English language teachers are among the most critical factors determining the quality of language education. In non-native English-speaking contexts, such as the Republic of Uzbekistan and, specifically, its autonomous Republic of Karakalpakstan, the role of the EFL teacher has evolved from that of a traditional transmitter of grammatical rules into a facilitator of communicative competence, digital literacy, and intercultural awareness. This evolution is driven by significant national reforms, including the "Uzbekistan Strategy 2030," which emphasizes the development of human capital and the radical improvement of foreign language instruction across all levels of education ^[1].

For teachers in Karakalpakstan, this transition presents both unique challenges and unparalleled opportunities. The region's specific socio-economic conditions, coupled with its distinct linguistic heritage, necessitate a professional development (PD) framework that is not only robust but also contextually relevant. National initiatives, such as Presidential Decree No. 5117, have set high benchmarks by encouraging teachers to attain international certifications (such as IELTS C1) to ensure that their linguistic foundation meets the demands of modern classrooms. Furthermore, the introduction of the first-ever competency-based professional standards for teachers, developed with the support of UNICEF, highlights a shift toward a more service-oriented and professionalized teaching workforce ^[2].

Despite these policy advancements, the gap between ideal standards and the daily realities faced by many teachers remains significant. Issues such as uneven institutional support, a lack of specialized resources tailored to the Karakalpak context, and psychological barriers associated with high-stakes testing regimes can hinder professional growth. This article explores the current state of teacher competency and examines the impact of continuous professional development (CPD) programs—including international collaborations and local professional networks—on teaching practices in secondary and higher education institutions in Karakalpakstan ^[3].

LITERATURE REVIEW

Research on teacher competency and professional development in non-native English-speaking countries emphasizes the critical role of continuous professional learning in improving English language teaching quality. Teacher competency is commonly defined as a combination of subject knowledge, pedagogical skills, language proficiency, and professional attitudes (Richards, 2017).

In non-native English contexts, studies highlight that limited exposure to authentic English environments, insufficient language proficiency, and inadequate training opportunities remain persistent challenges (Borg, 2015).

The literature also underscores the importance of context-sensitive professional development models. Effective programs are characterized by sustained duration, practical orientation, collaboration, and alignment with teachers' classroom realities (Darling-Hammond et al., 2017).

In post-Soviet and Central Asian contexts, including Karakalpakstan, scholars note that professional development has traditionally been centralized and theory-oriented, with limited emphasis on reflective practice and learner-centered methodologies (Mukhametov & Yuldashev, 2020).

Recent studies stress the growing relevance of communicative language teaching, technology integration, and competency-based approaches in teacher development for non-native English countries. However, successful implementation depends on local adaptation, institutional support, and teachers' motivation for self-directed professional growth. Overall, the literature suggests that strengthening teacher competency in regions such as Karakalpakstan requires systematic, practice-oriented, and culturally responsive professional development frameworks.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This research employed a mixed-methods empirical design to investigate the influence of professional development on teacher competency in Karakalpakstan. The primary data source was a field study involving 50 novice English language teachers (with one to three years of teaching experience) working in secondary schools in the city of Nukus. These teachers participated in a structured online questionnaire that assessed the frequency of their engagement in CPD activities, the training formats they found most effective, and their self-reported improvements in areas such as classroom management, pedagogical knowledge, and teacher confidence. To provide a deeper institutional perspective, the study also incorporated data from the English Language and Literature Department at Nukus State Pedagogical Institute (NSPI). This component included semi-structured interviews with 15 faculty members and classroom observations focusing on the application of Communicative Language Teaching (CLT) and Task-Based Language Teaching (TBLT). In addition, a separate survey was administered to 23 English teachers and 13 history (content) teachers from both NSPI and Karakalpak State University to evaluate the level of teacher preparedness for Content and Language Integrated Learning (CLIL). The research further reviewed national-level professional training outcomes, specifically the "English Speaking Nation" (ESN) program and the British Council's "English for Teachers" initiatives. Legislative analysis was conducted on recent decrees concerning the transition to a qualification-based employment system, scheduled to take effect in 2027, which will require specialists to obtain formal competency certificates. Quantitative data were analyzed using descriptive statistical methods to identify trends in participation and performance, while qualitative data underwent thematic analysis to reveal the psychological and structural barriers to effective teacher development in the region.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

The data analysis reveals a high level of engagement with professional development among Karakalpak English teachers; however, its impact remains uneven across different institutional settings. In the Nukus novice teacher study, 70% of respondents reported participating in CPD activities within the past year. Workshops (56%), online courses (40%), and conferences (36%) were identified as the most frequently attended formats, with teachers reporting that these activities significantly boosted their confidence and classroom management skills. Furthermore, programs such as ESN have successfully trained over 18,000 teachers nationwide, with hundreds of Karakalpak educators receiving international TESOL certifications and becoming part of a growing network of teacher mentors ^[4].

Regarding linguistic competency, the study found that nearly half of all English teachers in Uzbekistan report a C1-level IELTS score, with a median score of 7.0. There is a moderate correlation between higher proficiency levels and greater satisfaction with salary and job security, reflecting the effectiveness of state incentives for certified teachers. However, a critical finding was the lack of correlation between linguistic proficiency and classroom confidence. Many teachers at the B2 level expressed a high sense of adequacy, while some C1-level teachers reported the need for additional pedagogical rather than linguistic training. This suggests that “linguistic competence” alone is insufficient; teachers require a broader set of “linguodidactic” competencies that integrate cultural awareness and technology use. At the university level, faculty members at NSPI demonstrated a strong commitment to international standards by participating in exchange programs and professional training with the British Council and institutions in the UK, the USA, and Germany. These initiatives have led to a predominantly task-based approach in the classroom, in which teachers employ authentic multimedia resources to engage students. Conversely, the survey of history teachers revealed a significant gap in preparedness for specialized instruction through CLIL. Most history teachers expressed uncertainty regarding the methodological changes required to teach their subject in English, citing both insufficient linguistic competence and a shortage of English-language materials specific to Karakalpak history ^[5].

The research also identified major systemic barriers to professional development. A lack of time (30%) was cited as the primary obstacle, followed by limited access to high-quality CPD in rural areas (24%) and financial constraints (16%). In some instances, teachers reported that institutional barriers—such as being denied time off for training—prevented them from participating in professional development opportunities. Psychological barriers, including the fear of making mistakes in front of students and peers, were also prevalent, particularly among novice teachers transitioning from theoretical studies to independent classroom practice. The findings suggest that the development of teacher competency in Karakalpakstan is currently in a state of “accelerated maturation,” in which top-down policy mandates intersect with bottom-up professional agency. High levels of engagement in programs such as NETRUZ and ESN indicate that teachers are eager to adopt modern methodologies, provided that adequate support and resources are available. The shift toward Exploratory Action Research is particularly significant, as it empowers teachers to move beyond the role of “technicians” and become “researchers” capable of diagnosing and addressing their own classroom challenges. This form of professional agency is essential for creating resilient language programs capable of withstanding the complex socio-economic fluctuations of the Aral Sea region ^[6].

A critical implication for future policy is the need for a contextualized and differentiated approach to CPD. While international methodologies such as CLT and TBLT are effective, they must be adapted to local linguistic and cultural realities. Teachers who incorporate Karakalpak culture and history into their English lessons report higher levels of student engagement, suggesting that intercultural competence should be a core component of teacher training. Furthermore, as the country moves toward a qualification-based employment system in 2027, professional development must evolve into a continuous lifecycle process rather than a series of isolated workshops. This includes strengthening mentoring and induction programs for novice teachers, which have been shown to reduce feelings of professional isolation and improve long-term retention. Preparedness for CLIL and EMI (English-Medium Instruction) remains a major bottleneck. The fundamental flaw identified—namely, that graduates are often unprepared for occupation-specific needs—requires a substantial redesign of both pre-service and in-service training for non-English faculty. Addressing this issue will necessitate the development of specialized teaching toolkits that include films, presentations, and articles adapted for the Karakalpak classroom, as well as joint training programs that enable collaboration between language teachers and content teachers. The success of future reforms, such as the transition to a 12-year school system, will largely depend on whether the “School Champions” and mentors developed through current programs can be effectively institutionalized as leaders within their local communities.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, teacher competency in Karakalpakstan is being progressively strengthened through a combination of linguistic certification, pedagogical innovation, and international collaboration. However, for these gains to be sustainable, institutional support must become more evenly distributed, and the specific socio-linguistic and resource-related challenges of the region must be systematically addressed. By fostering a culture of reflective practice and continuous inquiry, Karakalpakstan can develop a teaching workforce that is not only proficient in English but also capable of preparing the next generation to navigate the complexities of an increasingly globalized world.

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- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
 - 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
 - 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
 - 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
 - 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
 - 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
 - 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
 - 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
 - 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
 - 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
 - 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
 - 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
 - 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

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